

Artificial Nucleus with Leptons as its Constituents

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Abstract

Artificial nucleus creating model is briefly discussed using new theoretical techniques. This nuclear structure needs to be created artificially via special experimental techniques and arrangements. This note is a speculative prediction of such nuclear models which shall consist of particles of leptons group.

Keywords: ANF, Leptons, Counter Repulsion

In standard model and in reality leptons never interacts with strong force means it only interacts with gravitational force, weak force and electromagnetism. This note presents an essential but super weird idea to create tiny nuclear like sphere in which particles from lepton group say electrons are its fundamental constituents. Here we will use artificial way to produce consequence like protons together and neutrons makes up a nucleus. The electrons will be shown to interact as if it is due to strong interaction, but not strong interaction. The model in this note can be used as an artificial tool to develop such weird forms possibly into reality, however the experiments is almost very complex and we strongly feel that it is achievable. Isolate electrons from atoms (the state of ionization) and gather them together in a very tiny section like protons in nucleus and must be arranged similar to protons to evade the violation of exclusion principle. Some neutral leptons (electron neutrino) or composite states like neutrons* can also be added in artificial nucleus. Generally all electrons will possess a massive tendency to repel outside or outwards as like charges repel each other by emitting or absorbing photons essentially the rules of quantum electrodynamics. The technique here is as electrons approaches to sit in one place we

must create a uniform negatively charged field of constant magnitude or non uniform magnitude artificially and therefore must be of very very short range as in strong interaction in protons, such artificial negative field (ANF) will now acts inwards and tends to counter and compress the electrons together and thus overcoming initial repulsion in a small place in turn generating a tiny sphere like atomic nucleus. Clearly electrons and other neutral particles (if added) are surrounded by short range ANF and a method of "implosion" can be imagined which here is compared. However the strength of the ANF must be extremely high at least higher than electron's electric field and should be of relatively short range so that it can hold the leptons together in a tiny place. This ANF will create counter repulsion or this field will interact with electrons which are coming outwards and hold as if they are bound together with strong attractive force, a clear analogy with nuclear force. Therefore this idea essentially suggest that an artificial nucleus with stable leptons can be possible at least speculative in theory. This model can be called as "super dual lepton repulsion model" or SDLRM" and this artificial nucleus will split its electrons outside due to their own repulsion only and only when we turn off the artificial inward directing negative field. We propose this

crazy idea to the experimenters and requesting them to validate the model at least in accuracy of 1 or 0.1% or even less. We are unaware about the practical use of such obnoxious ideas but we do believe that this might be a new step towards a massive journey in understanding how universe works in microscopic and submicroscopic level and perhaps for better explaining quantum electrodynamics and mysteries and unknown behavior of leptons at least in theory.

*residue strong force of neutrons will not affect leptons as leptons does not participate in strong interaction.